

Table S7. Short-circuit currents and electrophysiologic parameters in PneumaCult differentiation media. Data represent short circuit current values for baseline currents and resistance of monolayers. Amiloride inhibited ENaC currents (Δ Amil), Forskolin/IBMX stimulated cAMP currents, CFTR_{inh}-172 inhibited currents (Δ Fsk + CFTR_{inh}-172), and ATP-activated currents (Δ ATP). Values represented are (mean $\pm$ SEM); D = Donor.

PN ALI	Baseline currents (μA/cm²)	Resistance (Ω.cm²)	ΔAmil (μA/cm²)	ΔFsk/IBMX (μA/cm²)	ΔFsk/IBMX + CFTR_{inh}172 (μA/cm²)	ΔATP (μA/cm²)
D1	-	-	-	-	-	-
D2	60.67 $\pm$ 11.23	88.77 $\pm$ 8.24	-15.73 $\pm$ 7.46	12.07 $\pm$ 3.95	-53.05 $\pm$ 6.48	7.74 $\pm$ 0.89
D3	26.88 $\pm$ 3.84	69.10 $\pm$ 5.29	-6.05 $\pm$ 1.26	7.47 $\pm$ 0.69	-26.52 $\pm$ 4.43	7.90 $\pm$ 2.51
D4	30.63 $\pm$ 1.018	117.6 $\pm$ 10.63	-11.48 $\pm$ 0.68	22.40 $\pm$ 1.93	-22.93 $\pm$ 2.84	7.28 $\pm$ 0.70
D5	16.10 $\pm$ 0.71	211.0 $\pm$ 28.29	-11.15 $\pm$ 0.74	7.78 $\pm$ 1.19	-12.99 $\pm$ 1.20	3.44 $\pm$ 0.55